

SOME ISSUES IN TEACHING ACTING TO MUSICAL THEATER STUDENTS

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Annotation: The article talks about the reading of literature in shaping the performance skills of the students of the "Theatre Art" faculty, and about illuminating the inner experiences of the characters of the stage through the works. Some methodological guidelines are also discussed.

Key words: range, timbre, dynamics, method, conductor, arietta, arioso, romance, duet.

Аннотация: В статье говорится о чтении литературы в формировании исполнительского мастерства студентов факультета «Театральное искусство», а также о освещении через произведения внутренних переживаний героев сцены. Обсуждаются также некоторые методические рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: диапазон, тембр, динамика, метод, дирижер, ариетта, ариозо, романс, дуэт.

Personal reading is important for the development of a person. Reading fiction, in particular, is extremely useful in the formation and improvement of students' worldview, in independent thinking, in expressing their attitude to events in the world. A person can expand his thinking only through books. Within the framework of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority areas of development of our country in 2017-2021, many laws and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan have been adopted over the past period, aimed at radically reforming all spheres of state and social life.

As is known, our country has long been a center of science and has made its contribution to world civilization. After the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 and the State Program for its implementation in the "Year of Human Dignity and Active Neighborhood" were approved and announced by the decree of our President, not long after, on February 2, another important document, the signing of the resolution "On additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art", once again confirms the serious attention paid by the head of our state to the spheres of spirituality, culture, and art. Our university is also a center of science, technology, culture, and education. In this institution, our students study in 24 undergraduate areas of study, including the musical theater acting department of the "Theater Arts" faculty, which has been educating students for many years. Despite the rapid

acceleration of the times and globalization, the traditions and values of the teacher and student still continue. Musical knowledge, awareness of classical literature, their service in teaching young people the qualities of humanity in their spiritual and moral lives and in growing up as perfect people is unlimited and incomparable. For many years, our highly qualified professors and teachers have been teaching the subject of "Vocal" and skillfully teaching the secrets of their profession. The main task of the subject of "Vocal" is to educate young people in the spirit of aesthetics and love for the homeland through the means of singing art. They have been educating hundreds of young talents and helping them find their place in independent life. What is the role of musical education for students studying in the direction of musical drama?

Students who want to master this field need musical ability, hearing, singing, imagination, thinking, feeling, feeling the method, a deep understanding and respect for their chosen profession, the ability to remember, striving for the goal and, of course, discipline. This is based on a lot of hard work in the process of studying and in future work. First of all, they need to study with a professional teacher, the teacher must be able to see the talent in the student, correctly assess it, and correctly direct it. They need to work on the vocal range and provide the right works. Musical theater actors are taught songs, ariosos, ariettas, arias, duets, trios, romances and various repertoires from musical dramas, enriching the teaching process. The majority of students of our university, that is, students studying at this faculty, carry out their work activities in the theaters of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As we all know, in musical drama theaters, all stage performances are performed live. A musical theater actor must be young, handsome, with a good voice, a wide range of vocal abilities, be able to concentrate, have a strong memory, constantly work on himself, search, and strive for innovation in his work. An actor faces some problems when performing musical dramas performed by a live orchestra. Singing is a natural process, and the performer is required to have a smooth sound that can be heard in every corner of the hall. He must be able to start the work on time, perform it in a manner that is consistent with the conductor's instructions, sing clearly without separating from the orchestra, and feel the rhythm, meter, dynamic characteristics, and loudness of the work. The actor must not only take into account the character of the work being sung, but also include the stage movements. He must have the vocal power to break through the pressure of the orchestra with his voice. We all know that in theaters, all librettos are written on the piano, which requires musical literacy from the performer. We know that

most students studying musical theater acting do not have musical literacy, although the works performed on stage involve heroes of the time, singing arias and romances. It would certainly be appropriate for the actor to work independently on himself, to do voice warm-up exercises on his own. For this, it would be appropriate to include solfeggio and piano in the educational process during the 4-year undergraduate studies. Reading plays written for musical drama plays a special place in creating the hero of his work. Each student and student would create a real hero of the time only if he read more books related to his field.

In conclusion, the role of a student who reads books in the correct formation of his thinking as a person is incomparable. The information and resource center system of our university has been actively established. All types of world, classic, and classical literature are available in electronic form in various languages.

As Abdulla Oripov said - "The sea will shine for the first time with the torch of Beruni's mind"

The library continues to increase its status as a place of enlightenment, a center of knowledge and enlightenment.

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